
Romieg Soca

Taxonomy: *Ophrys atrata* or *incubacea* ?

Keywords

Orchidaceae; Ophrys atrata, O. incubacea; Taxonomy.

Zusammenfassung

Soca, R. (2001): Taxonomie: *Ophrys atrata* oder *incubacea*.- Jour. Eur. Orch. 33(1): 447- 455.

Die Chronologie der Beschreibung von *Ophrys atrata* wird zusammengestellt.

Summary

Soca, R. (2001): Taxonomie: *Ophrys atrata* or *incubacea*.- Jour. Eur. Orch. 33(1): 447- 455.

The chronology of the description of *Ophrys atrata* is summarized.

Riassunto

Soca, R. (2001): Tassonomia: *Ophrys atrata* o *incubacea*.- Jour. Eur. Orch. 33(1): 447- 455.

La cronologia delle descrizioni tassonomiche a proposito di *Ophrys atrata* viene esposta.

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Introduction

Before attempting to classify, are we sure that we do know which taxon we are talking about? Doing so, are we sure that we are on the same wavelength, both with each other and with the describer?

I believe it is a prerequisite for plant classification, mapping, conservation, etc.

I have been looking for the protologues and associated samples for fifteen years. Among the perplexing dilemmas existing in the genus *Ophrys*, I have chosen a well-known one, namely *Ophrys atrata* or *incubacea*.

Chronological review

First a brief chronological review, which I shall illustrate with some slides and comments.

The epithet *atrata* was first used for an *Ophrys* by LINNAEUS in 1767.

The plant was collected by Schreber in South Africa and does not belong to the genus *Ophrys* in the present meaning. It was subsequently renamed *Ceratandra atrata* by Durand & Schinz in 1892. *Ophrys atrata* L. was lectotypified in CAFFERTY & JARVIS (1999) by Linder: Herb. Linn. No. 1056.31 (LINN).

In 1800, SWARTZ issued a revision of *Orchidaceae*. He only maintained ten *Ophrys* species, among which *O. crucigera* Jacquin. It seems that the Jacquin's icon (1781) representing *Ophrys crucigera* is not related to our *Ophrys*.

In 1821, STEUDEL mentions *Pterygodium atratum* as a synonym with *Ophrys atrata* in the first issue of the *Nomenclator Botanicus*.

In 1827, LINDLEY describes *Ophrys atrata* from plants which Mauri sent him from the Roma area; that name was illegitimate ever since it was published. LINDLEY did know that *Ophrys atrata* was already used by LINNAEUS, but the botanical code did not exist and the way of thinking was different; as just mentioned, a synonym with the LINNAEUS' binomial had already been proposed. From 1827, the epithet *atrata* was unanimously adopted for naming a Mediterranean taxon.

In 1842, TODARO described *Arachnites incubacea* in his book about Sicilian orchids from a letter which his friend Bianca sent him.

In 1842, BIANCA described *Ophrys incubacea*. In his paper, which was published after the TODARO's book, he proposed that name as a synonym with both *Arachnites fuciflora ambigua* and Cupani's *Orchis psitacu vespa arra*. The description corresponds to *Ophrys incubacea-atrata* in the present meaning. On the data label of a herbarium sheet, which was found at Firenze, he proposed that name as a synonym with *Ophrys atrata*.

In 1844, GUSSONE, said he couldn't have any opinion, since he had been given a specimen in a poor condition.

In 1882, NYMAN mentioned *O. biceratia* Delile, *O. cyanogramma* Welwitsch and *O. incubacea* Bianca as synonyms with *Ophrys atrata*.

I have found two sheets with a description of *Ophrys biceratia* Delile at the Montpellier herbarium (MPU); some plants were collected by D. Touchy and Esprit Fabre at Agde in April 1824, April 1825, April 1833. That binomial

cannot be used (Art. 34.1.c). A sheet with a description was also found at the Paris herbarium (P) (the plant was collected in April 1832).

I don't know what the *Ophrys cyanogramma* Welwitsch is related to, but that binomial cannot be used (Art. 34.1.c).

Subsequently, many authors gave different combinations for naming our taxon:

In 1894, ARCANGELI: *O. aranifera* subsp. *atrata* Arcangeli.

In 1895, Index Kewensis mentioned *Ceratandra chloroleuca* Ecklon ex Bauer 1837 as a valid name for *O. atrata* Linnaeus 1767 not Lindley, what is inconsistent with the rules of the botanical code.

In 1901, BUBANI: *Arachnites atrata* Bubani.

1908, LOJACONO showed a sheet in which *Ophrys atrata* and *Ophrys incubacea* were quite different from each other.

In 1910, BRIQUET: *O. sphecodes* (Miller) var. *atrata* (Lindl.) Briquet.

In 1923, FIORI: *O. aranifera* (Hudson) subsp. *atrata* (Lindl.) Fiori.

In 1928, CAMUS: *O. aranifera* subsp. *atrata* Camus.

In 1940, SOÓ named *O. incubacea* within *O. araneifera*, but not as a subspecies and *O. araneifera* subsp. *atrata* for which he mentioned many synonyms.

In 1952, MAYER: *O. sphecodes* subsp. *atrata* Mayer.

In 1976, MALAGARRIGA: *O. sphecodes* (Miller) subsp. *atrata* (Lindl.) HTMalag.

Lastly, in 1986, BAUMANN & KÜNKELE gave *Ophrys incubacea* as a valid name.

One may wonder why BAUMANN & KÜNKELE replaced *Ophrys atrata* with *Ophrys incubacea*, since all the Sicilian authors - TODARO, BIANCA, GUSSONE, LOJACONO - mentioned *atrata* and *incubacea* as two separate species.

The history of the Bianca's herbarium can be found in the book written by GAUDIOSO (1996), from Ragusa. It can be summarised as follows: Signora Angela Auricchia, from Avola, went on a course at the dipartimento di Biologia et Ecologia Vegetale di Catania. She convinced the Bianca's heir and the herbarium material, which was still at Avola, was transferred to Catania. Since the Bianca's death, no botanist had access to his herbarium, which not yet available. Rosario Galesi (Dipartimento di Biologia ed Ecologia Vegetale di Catania) promised me that I shall be informed first when it is possible.

As a conclusion, we cannot assert yet that *Ophrys incubacea* Bianca is the valid name in place of *Ophrys atrata* Lindley, even though Bianca himself considered it was the same taxon (in sheet but not in text). I have visited several herbaria - Geneva, Montpellier, Palermo, Paris, Roma - in which I could not find any Bianca's sheet of *Ophrys incubacea*.

Acknowledgements

I want to express my thanks to all the people who helped me for that study: Riccardo M. Baldini (Firenze herbarium), Jacques Florence (Paris), Rosario Galesi (Niscemi), Fernand Jacquemoud (Geneva herbarium), François Jacquet (Paris), Michel Kerguelen (Paris), Anna Millozza (Roma herbarium), Thierry Pain (Paris), Rolando Romolini (Firenze), Peter A. Schäfer (Montpellier herbarium), Rodolfo Picchi Sermolli (Firenze).

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Fig. 1: LINDLEY J., 1827. Botanical Register 13: 1087
planche couleur

Fig. 2: LOJACONO POJERO M., 1908. -Flora Sicula. tome 3: 5-53
extrait planche 1

praetium duximus, ut inde res queat enucleari a doctis.

Quid judicandum de synonymo (*Ophrys bombiflora* Link, et Reich. icon. cent. 9. p. 24 t. 116) a cl. Gussone huic nostrae speciei relato, ut ab ipso amicissimus idem Todaro se in literis accepisse confitetur? — Revera huic allucinatione ansam praebuit speciminis sicci fallax inspectio, ex qua visum est (id mihi ipso Todaro confirmante in epistolis) labellum pseudo-3-lobum, lobis lateralibus adnatis: quod omnino commentitium demonstravimus. Profecto enim gibberi, compressione ad latera dejecti, loborum imaginem mentili sunt, proque lobis sumpti!!

III.

Ophrys Incubacca, Bianca in Tod. Orch. Sic. p. 75 sub Arachnide Fuciflora.

O. radice scroliformi, tuberculis ovalis, perigonii segmentis exterioribus oblongis glabris, interioribus puberulis dimidio minoribus linearibus abruptis, margine undulato-crispo: labello ovali convexo bilobo, nulla appendice, marginibus villosis tumido-revolutis, disco lineolis violaceis inscripto in formam gabali, gibba conica mediana utrinque prominente.

Syn. = *Arachnites fuciflora* ♂ ambigua, *Tod. op.cit. p. 75.* Nomen vernaculum nullum. Ex naturali Orchidearum familia.

Habitat in collibus, sed rara. Copiose legitur al Cozzo di Alessi.

Floret Martio Aprili. V

Radix didyma, tuberculis ovalis, vel subrotundis cum fibris superimpositis.

Scapus $1\frac{1}{2}$ - $1\frac{1}{2}$ pedalis (spica supputata) teres, basi foliosus.

Folia radicalia priora oblonga humo adpressa, caetera erecta, lanceolata, caulina basi vaginantia, superiora minora, omnia nervoso-striata, integra, obtuse carinata, laete virentia.

Flores inodori 4 - 12, alterni, in spica laxa bracteata, intervallo 2 - pollicari.

Bractea foliaceae virides, lanceolatae, involutae, ovario subaequales, in floribus supereminis breviores.

Perigonii segmenta viridi-glaucis, tria exteriora 6 - 8 linearia, pellucido-glandulosa oblonga (non ovato-oblonga) obtusa, in triangulum patentia, concavo-subincurva, marginibus revolutis, lateralibus saepe fusco-maculatis, in omnibus nervo carinali externe viridiores; interiora linearia (interdum basi ovata) abrupta, divaricate-patula (non vero patentiuscula, *Tod.*) exterioribus dimidio breviora, margine undulato-crispo subrevoluta, in pagina superiore puberulo-tomentosa, colore saturatiore.

Labellum atro-purpureum, ad anussim ovale (non obovatum) 2-lobum (non revera emarginatum), nulla appendice interjecta, marginibus villosis tumido-revolutis, gibba conica; $1\frac{1}{2}$ lineari quasi mediana utroque latere extuberante, antice inclinata, alia ab alia nonnihil divergente, utrisque ad axillas glabris, extus villosis ut margo labelli. Hoc autem in disco glabrum, duabus lineolis pa-

Fig. 3: BIANCA J., (1841) 1842. - Novae plantarum Species, minusve in Sicilia cognitae, prope Hyblam vulgo Avola sponte provenientes. Giornale del Cabinetto Letterario dell'Accademia Gioenia 7: 52-63

Fig. 3a: pag. 58-59

rallielis violaceis verticalibus notatum, quas tertia transversalis superne conjungit in formam gabali. Anguli, quos haec tertia linea verticalibus insistens utrinque facit, interne fornicati, externae vix lineam vel ad summum sesquilineam sursum acuminato producti. Item linea transversalis in medio sursum aliquando angulato-dentata; reliquae dilatato-spatulatae ad basim, quae obtusa vel acuta evadit, et ex parte inferiore, vel saepius hinc inde 1-angulata.

Gynostemium breve, vix 3-1/2, - 4 lineare, leniter assurgens in labellum. Inferius *gynixi* cavum, atro colore labelli suffusum, eleganter maculis albis notatur, duabus anticis hinc inde ad latera *staminodiorum*, altera centrali intimiore. Area *gynixi* alba. *Bursiculae*, *retinacula*, et *caudiculae*, flava. *Septula*, et *locelli* flavo-rufescentia. *Massae pollinicae* luteae. *Clinandrium* ad latera massas pollinicas protegentia membranaceum flavum, extus linea dorsali viridi excurrente usque ad verticem, qui breviter, rostratus, horizontaliter prosistit in labellum.

Diplogia pollicaris.

Semina minutissima scobiformia.

Amicissimus Augustinus Todaro (op. cit.) suspensus est ex speciminibus siccis, et ex meo dubio hanc speciem ad *O. Araniferam* *Huds.* nonnihil accedere, ideoque ut varietatem suae *Arachnitis fuciflorae* retulit, sed non absque hesitatione. Ego autem existimo, labello nusquam 3-lobo, gibberum et operculorum forma, aliisque notis, ipsoque praesertim habitu adhuc ab illa discriminari.

In Todari adumbratione nonnullae hallucinationes irrepserunt ob observationem non satis firmam ex speciminibus exsiccatis.

De synonymo Cupani (*Orchis psittacu vespa arva*, *Panph. sic.* 3. t. 115, et ex bibl. Cat. 2. t. 221) huic nostrae speciei ab ipso amicissimo Todaro cum dubio relato, nullum valeo proferre iudicium, nam ego Cupani opus non vidi, ideoque nec iconem.

IV.

Ophrys Lunulata, *Parl. Giorn. di Scien. Lett. e Arti per la Sicil.* vol. 62 p. 4 e *Rar. pl. fasc. 1 p. 13 t. 2 f. 3.*

O. radice scrotiformi, tuberculis ovatis perigonii segmentis exterioribus glabris, lateralibus ovato-oblongis, medio oblongo, interioribus basi puberulis, linearibus, brevioribus, labello leviter 3-lobo, macula quadrata antica fornicata notato, lobis lateralibus oblongis villosis dependentibus, basi gibbo-extumidis, medio lato convexo replicato, apice emarginato appendiculato, appendicula carnea incurva.

Syn = *Arachnites lunulata*, *Tod. Orch.*

Sic. p. 77.

Ophrys replicata, *Nob. ined.*

Vulgo prorsus ignota vernaculo nomine non gaudet.

Ex naturali Orchidearum familia.

Habitat in vallibus collinis (*Cava del l' Amico*, *Spina*).

Floret Aprili Maio V

Fig. 3: BIANCA J., (1841) 1842. - Novae plantarum Species, minusve in Sicilia cognitae, prope Hyblam vulgo Avola sponte provenientes. *Giornale del Cabinetto Letterario dell'Accademia Gioenia* 7: 52-63

Fig. 3b: pag. 60-61